

Research Article

Conceptual Design of Smart Cat Feeder

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Abstract: *In today's fast-paced world, automation technology is advancing rapidly, becoming more accessible, intuitive, and easy to manage. For pet owners, especially those who cherish the company of cats, this technology can bring peace of mind. A new prototype has been developed to help cat owners ensure their pets are well-fed and hydrated, even when they are away from home. This system, powered by a microcontroller, allows owners to conveniently schedule their cat's feeding and water supply. The food is stored in a dispenser, controlled by a DC motor that regulates the amount released into the bowl. The bowl is placed on a load cell to monitor the food's weight in real time, ensuring precise portions. Owners can set feeding times and food quantities through the user-friendly app, adjusting based on the current food level in the bowl. Additionally, the system monitors the water container using a sensor, automatically refilling it when needed. With this innovative solution, pet owners can relax, knowing their cats are always taken care of with the right amount of food and water, ensuring their well-being no matter the owner's schedule.*

Keywords: Food Dispenser; Water Dispenser; Smart Feeder

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1. INTRODUCTION

Keeping pets at home is very prevalent in Malaysia. Although there are no true statistics to back this up, everyday observations show that many households have pets, and some even have more than one. Owning pets may indeed be a tremendously joyful experience, but it also presents problems, particularly for those with little to no experience. This is because caring for a pet involves patience and a lot of love. Common issues in pet care include inconsistent feeding hours, which can have an impact on pets' psychological and physiological health, as well as a lack of guidance in selecting the proper amount of food.

Pet care is routinely and carefully managing a pet's physical, emotional, and dietary requirements to sustain their overall well-being. Physically, pets require regular exercise, a clean living environment, and sufficient veterinarian care to avoid infections and injuries. Pets thrive emotionally on companionship, affection, and mental stimulation, all of which serve to minimize stress-related behaviours and promote excellent mental health. This part of care is especially important for social animals such as dogs and cats, which might develop behavioural issues if they are emotionally neglected. According to studies, interactions with pets can significantly reduce stress and anxiety, benefiting both the pet and the owner by creating a calming environment and promoting mental well-being (NIH, 2023; Esposito, 2019).

Regularly feeding balanced, species-appropriate meals to pets is crucial for preventing malnutrition and obesity, both of which are typical issues caused by poor nutritional management. A well-balanced diet supports overall health and helps maintain an appropriate weight, minimizing the risk of serious health issues such as heart disease, diabetes, and arthritis (Kirk et al., 2020; Scherk et al., 2019). Veterinary specialists emphasize the importance of a balanced diet in preventing pet obesity, which can be avoided by monitoring food intake and adhering to regular feeding schedules (Lund et al., 2018; McGowan et al., 2020). Providing vital nutrition to pets can help them live longer and healthier lives (Scherk et al., 2019; Lund et al., 2018).

Monitoring food intake and keeping to regular feeding schedules are critical for keeping pets healthy and preventing obesity. One effective strategy is to use automated feeders, which allow owners to program exact amount sizes and feeding timings, resulting in constant meal intervals (McGowan et al., 2020). Furthermore, keeping a careful record of daily food intake can assist notice changes in appetite, and establishing a schedule gives pets a sense of security (American Veterinary Medical Association, n.d.). Accurate portion measurement is critical, since using a measuring cup or scale can help prevent overfeeding (Lund et al. 2018). Regular weight checks help to monitor progress and alter quantities as needed while consulting a veterinarian can provide personalised dietary advice based on the pet's individual health needs (Scherk et al., 2019). Together, these methods can help with appropriate feeding control and overall pet well-being.

There are various unique devices for monitoring and regulating pet feeding. One famous example is a smart pet feeder that employs Internet of Things (IoT) technology and can be configured to administer exact amounts of food dependent on the pet's weight. This device frequently has two operational modes: a smart mode, in which the volume of food delivered is automatically regulated, and a control mode, which permits manual feeding (Borwornyot Sutam et al., 2020) (IJETT).

Another example is a mobile monitoring system for an automatic cat feeder that runs on a Raspberry Pi. This system has a webcam for real-time monitoring and a stepper motor that controls the dispensing mechanism. It enables pet owners to remotely monitor feeding activities using a smartphone app, ensuring they receive their food on time (International Journal of Modern Developments in Engineering and Science, 2023) (IJMDES).

One study developed a smart pet monitoring and feeding system that utilized a feedback control mechanism. The system is controlled by a microcontroller and can measure the food weight dispensed using load cells. It allows for precise control over the feeding process, ensuring that pets receive the right amount of food at designated times (Hisham et al., 2020). Moreover, another paper discussed integrating machine learning algorithms to enhance pet care, enabling the feeder to learn from the pet's eating patterns and adjust feeding schedules accordingly (Choi & Lee, 2022). These advancements illustrate the growing trend in pet care technology, helping pet owners manage their pets' dietary needs more effectively and efficiently. Unfortunately, water feeding is not integrated into these devices.

Pets' health and well-being also depend on access to fresh, clean water. Hydration is essential for several body activities, such as digestion, temperature regulation, and waste removal. A steady supply of water helps to prevent dehydration, which can lead to major health concerns such as kidney problems, urinary tract infections, and other consequences (Cohen et al., 2019; Hargis, 2020).

Consider using a pet-specific water fountain to keep your pets properly hydrated. These devices circulate water, which may encourage pets to drink more owing to the enticing sound and movement of the water. According to studies, pets are more willing to drink from a fountain rather than a stagnant bowl, which promotes greater hydration. Furthermore, changing the water and

cleaning the bowl or fountain regularly can help prevent bacteria and algae growth, guaranteeing a healthy drinking environment (Hargis, 2020).

Some smart pet feeders have a water reservoir feature, which allows owners to measure how much water their pets consume while also ensuring they always have access to fresh water (Choi & Lee, 2022). Smart pet feeders with water reservoir features not only provide convenience but also serve as valuable tools for health monitoring, ensuring pets remain hydrated and healthy.

Based on our literature review, we conclude the problem statement for automatic cat feeding can be established by addressing three essential scenarios. First, current cat dietary concerns frequently include obstacles such as overfeeding and underfeeding, both of which can result in nutritional deficiencies and health problems. Second, specific concerns with present feeders may include food being stuck, inappropriate portion control, limited food storage, and the inability to monitor the cat's diet in real-time. Third, food feeding is not integrated with water supply to cats. To solve these concerns, an innovative way would be to design a device-controlled system that integrates with an application. This device would allow for exact data gathering and analysis of the cat's feeding habits, resulting in improved nutritional management and general cat health. As a result, this technology enables cat keeper to monitor their pets' feeding habits via their smartphones even when they are not around. It will provide an overview of automatic feeder technology for cats, including its functionality, advantages, and potential impact on pet care practices.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Cat feeders are essential for providing sufficient nutrition and health to feline friends. There are several types of feeders available to accommodate varied eating patterns and lifestyles. Automatic feeders distribute pre-set portions at predetermined times, which is especially useful for maintaining regular feeding schedules and avoiding overeating. For example, the Whisker Feeder-Robot can carry up to 32 cups of food and allows for meal amount customisation (A-Z Animals, 2023). Gravity feeders, on the other hand, give a constant flow of food, allowing cats to graze all day, whereas microchip feeders prevent food theft in multi-pet households by only opening for specific pets. Additionally, wet food feeders frequently include ice packs to retain freshness, and portion control feeders are critical for controlling specific nutritional demands.

An excellent example of a cat feeder that includes a water feature is the PetSafe Healthy Pet Food Station. This innovative feeder not only dispenses dry food through a gravity system but also offers an optional water reservoir that allows cats to have constant access to fresh water. The unit can be enhanced with a carbon filter to ensure clean drinking water, promoting better hydration and overall health for pets. This dual functionality makes it a convenient solution for pet owners looking to streamline feeding and watering their feline companions (A-Z Animals, 2023).

An innovative method of pet care is designing an autonomous pet food and water dispenser that improves feeding convenience while also allowing owners to monitor their pets. The device uses a Raspberry Pi 3B+ and a pump attached to a relay powered by a servo motor to efficiently distribute water. In addition to providing hydration, the dispenser has swivel-mounted cameras, allowing pet owners to monitor their pets during feeding times and make calls as needed. This combination of technology not only ensures that pets receive their meals and water on time, but it also provides owners with peace of mind while keeping a check on their furry companions (Kulaikar, 2023).

In this study, three common types of cat feeders come to mind: interactive feeders, automatic feeders with app control, and gravity feeders. Because gravity feeders have fewer mechanical parts and a straightforward design, they are usually the least expensive alternative. They are lightweight and

typically compact, making them ideal for tiny living areas. They are also easy to move and arrange. Additionally, because gravity feeders don't have any mechanical parts, they run silently, which makes them perfect for pets that are sensitive to noise. While they lack sophisticated features like portion control or scheduling, maintenance is still rather simple for owners—all they need to do is occasionally clean the unit and replenish the food container.

Conversely, interactive feeders come in a range of pricing points based on their features and intricacy, such as puzzles that encourage a cat's innate hunting instincts. However, they are typically more expensive. Because of their elaborate designs, these feeders typically weigh more and take up more room. Some make noise when cats play with the machinery or when food is supplied, but most run silently. More work goes into maintenance; owners must make sure that any electronic parts are operating correctly and clean the mechanisms frequently to keep food particles from getting stuck.

Since they combine cutting-edge technology and convenience, automatic feeders with app control often have the highest price tag of the three. The size of these feeders varies, but because they have electrical parts like motors and Wi-Fi connectivity, they are typically bigger, heavier, and less portable. They may make noises when administering or adjusting settings, thus noise levels can be an issue. Apart from this, maintenance includes making sure the electronic parts work properly, changing the batteries when necessary, and maintaining clean feeding mechanisms to avoid obstructions. Because every type of cat feeder has pros and cons of its own, the ideal option ultimately comes down to the owner's budget, the cat's demands and behaviour, and the amount of connection they hope to have during feeding times.

A conceptual design must be developed, and this requires concise machine flowcharts. Because they offer a clear, and visual representation of procedures, flowcharts are helpful in system design because they make it simpler to identify potential issues and enhance functionality (Henderson, 2018). Moreover, by outlining every stage of the process, flowcharts assist developers in troubleshooting and successfully communicating their ideas (Booch, 2018).

Figure 1 can be used as a reference throughout the entire discussion of matters. An autonomous pet food and water dispenser system simplifies the feeding process for pets while also meeting their hydration demands. The system starts by checking the food level and using sensors to determine whether there is an appropriate supply. If food is present, the system checks the water level, ensuring that fresh water is also available. If there is insufficient food or water, the device will notify the pet owner right away. When both supplies are confirmed, the dispenser operates, delivering the required amount of food and dispensing water via a connected pump. This setup not only provides for timely feedings, but it also has a monitoring feature that allows owners to see their pets in real-time via a phone application. Following dispensing, the device enters a feedback loop, checking for operational problems and guaranteeing a consistent feeding schedule, thus improving the entire pet care experience.

Figure 1. Flow Chart Cat’s Food and Water Dispenser.

3. FINDINGS

According to the objectives and scope of this study, the Pugh matrix has been used to choose the best method to apply. Table 1 shows the decision made by the Pugh matrix according to the discussion in 2.0.

Table 1. Pugh matrix.

Criteria	Weighing	Gravity Feeder	Interactive Feeder	Automatic Feeder Assisted by App Control
Size	2	5	4	3
Weight	2	5	3	2
Cost	3	4	3	2
Noise	3	4	3	2
Maintenance	5	1	2	3
Portion Control	5	1	2	4
Total Score		54	52	57

All things considered, the Automatic Feeder Assisted by App Control is the best alternative for people searching for a dependable and easy-to-use solution. The design integrates some components to provide the best possible outcome for the cat's consuming system as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Automatic Cat Feeder sketch design.

4. DISCUSSION

According to Table 1, The Pugh matrix weighs each of the six criteria — size, weight, cost, noise, maintenance, and portion control — to compare three different types of pet feeders: the Gravity Feeder, Interactive Feeder, and Automatic Feeder Assisted by App Control. With a weight of five each, maintenance and portion control are regarded as the most crucial components. The Gravity Feeder performs best in terms of size and weight, but it is less effective in terms of upkeep and portion management. The Interactive Feeder does not stand out in any one category, but its overall results are balanced. Conversely, the Automatic Feeder Assisted by App Control has a lower weight, size, and cost rating but excels in the two most important categories: maintenance and portion control.

The Automatic Feeder Assisted by App Control, with a total score of 57, beats out the Gravity Feeder (54) and Interactive Feeder (52) to become the best choice out of the three. This review highlights how important it is to include technology in pet feeding solutions because the Automatic Feeder not only satisfies pet owners' practical demands but also offers cutting-edge capabilities that improve feeding experiences for both pets and their owners.

Based on that, we designed a smart cat feeder with included the food and water dispenser. As we can see from Figure 2, the water feed section and the food container's shape are taken into consideration in this sketch. It leads the development process, serves as a visual representation of the suggested solution, and notifies stakeholders of the features of the finished product. A creative cat feeder's design offers some benefits that meet the various requirements of pet owners.

First of all, its small size makes it easy to move around, making it suitable for use in a variety of locations, including at home or on the go. This feeder's wireless capabilities allow pet owners to

remotely monitor and manage feeding schedules through smartphone applications, providing greater flexibility and guaranteeing that pets are fed on schedule even when their owners are not there. Furthermore, gathering detailed information on a pet's feeding routines offers insightful information that lets pet owners modify schedules and portion sizes to support the best possible health and well-being.

Furthermore, the feeder's design makes it straightforward to operate, allowing pets and their owners to engage with it without difficulty and lowering the possibility of stress associated with feeding. Its ergonomic design makes the feeder more desirable for daily usage by improving user comfort and encouraging frequent interaction. The use of eco-friendly materials highlights a dedication to sustainability, attracting ecologically aware customers who value ethical pet care options. All things considered, these design standards result in a multipurpose, easy-to-use cat feeder that successfully tackles the pragmatic and moral issues associated with contemporary pet ownership.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the development process of an automatic feeder for cats involves several critical steps to ensure the product's reliability, safety, and effectiveness. By conducting a comprehensive study to understand the specific needs and preferences of both cats and their owners, designers can create tailored solutions that align with diverse lifestyles and dietary requirements. The iterative prototyping and testing phases allow for continuous refinement of design concepts, ensuring that essential features such as customizable feeding schedules, portion control, and safety measures are effectively integrated. The final product is crafted with high-quality materials that emphasize sustainability, ease of maintenance, and durability, ultimately delivering a dependable feeding solution that enhances the well-being of pets while meeting the expectations of their owners. This holistic approach not only promotes healthier feeding practices but also contributes to a more responsible pet care ecosystem.

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